

STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART VII. ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF TERESANTALIC ACID AND TRICYCLOEKASANTALIC ACID

By P. C. GUHA AND S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

The electrochemical properties of teresantalic acid and tricycloekasantalic acid have been studied. It has been found that there is a direct relationship existing between steric hindrance and the strength of acids.

As a prelude to a systematic study of the different acids of the santalol series for determining the influence of ring structure on the general characteristics of the compounds, electrochemical properties of teresantalic acid and tricycloekasantalic acid (*vide infra* for formulae) have been studied. An interesting relationship existing between steric hindrance and ionisation constant observed in this connection has been discussed at the end of this paper. A drum-roller meter bridge was used in these experiments described in this connection.

Teresantalic acid was isolated from sandalwood oil according to the method of Soden and Muller (*Pharm. Z.*, 1899, **44**, 258) and was purified by fractional distillation under vacuum and then by crystallisation twice from petrol-ether; m.p. 157°; b.p. 127°/1 mm.; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -76.5^\circ$ (in benzene).

Solubility.—A saturated solution of the substance in conductivity water was prepared by shaking an excess of the powdered acid in water for 48 hours and the amount of substance in solution was determined by conductometric titration with standard alkali as shown graphically in Fig. 1 (curve 1). Solubility calculated from the graph was 4.9×10^{-3} g. mol. per litre at 22.8°.

Mobility and absolute velocity of the anion were determined by measuring the conductivity of the sodium salt of the acid at different dilutions. The salt solution was prepared by adding the acid in a standard solution of alkali. To prevent hydrolysis a slight excess of the free acid was always kept in suspension. The data obtained are presented in Fig. 2 (curve 1) as equivalent conductivity against \sqrt{C} . Λ_∞ (as found from the graph) was 68.85 mho at 22.8°. This tallies fairly well with the value 69.26, obtained by calculation from the Kohlrausch's formula ($\Lambda_\infty = \Lambda_c + b\sqrt{C}$). Therefore the mobility of the anion was $68.85 - L_{Na} = 68.85 - 48.21 = 20.64$. Hence the absolute velocity of the anion was $20.64/96,500 = 21.4 \times 10^{-5}$ cm./sec. at 22.8°.

Degree of Ionisation and Ionisation Constant.—The mean of several estimations of the specific conductivity of the saturated solution of the acid in conductivity water (specific conductivity 0.68×10^{-6} mho) at 22.8° was found to be 6.54×10^{-5} and subtracting the conductivity due to the solvent that of the acid is $(6.536 \times 10^{-4} - 0.68 \times 10^{-6}) = 6.47 \times 10^{-5}$.

Hence its equivalent conductivity $\Lambda = \frac{6.47 \times 10^{-5} \times 1000}{4.9 \times 10^{-3}} = 13.2$. Therefore, the degree of ionisation $\alpha = \Lambda/\Lambda_\infty = 13.2/20.64 + 337.5$ ($L_{Na} = 0.0368$). Therefore the ionisation constant

$$k = \frac{\alpha^2 c}{1 - \alpha} = \frac{(0.0368)^2 \times 0.0049}{1 - 0.0368} = 0.69 \times 10^{-5} \text{ at } 22.8^\circ.$$

Tricycloekasantalic acid was prepared by the oxidation of sandalwood oil with potassium permanganate according to the method of Semmler (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 1120). It was purified by crystallising once from alcohol and twice from petrol-ether, m.p. 76.4° (Semmler, m.p. 72°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +15.4^\circ$ (in alcohol). The electrochemical properties of the acid and its salt were determined exactly as in the previous case.

Solubility.—Conductometric titration of the saturated solution of the acid in conductivity water has been shown graphically in Fig. 1 (curve 2). The solubility found from the graph was 7.1×10^{-4} g. mol. per litre.

Mobility and Absolute Velocity of the Anion.—The equivalent conductivity of the sodium salt of the acid in presence of slight excess of suspended acid at different dilution was determined as previously and the relation between Λ and \sqrt{C} has been shown in Fig. 2 (curve 2). Λ_{∞} found from the graph = 65.35 (from Kohlrausch's formula, 65.01). Therefore, the mobility of the anion = $65.35 - L_{Na} = 63.35 - 48.21 = 17.14$. Hence the absolute velocity of the anion = $17.14/96,500 = 18.3 \times 10^{-5}$ cm./sec. at 22.8°.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

In figures curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to teresantallic acid and tricycloekasantallic acid.

Degree of Ionisation and Ionisation Constant.—The actual specific conductivity of the saturated solution of the acid was 3.32×10^{-5} mho (subtracting that of water). Therefore, the equivalent conductivity = $3.32 \times 10^{-5} \times 1000/0.00071 = 46.76$.

Hence the degree of ionisation

$$\alpha = \Lambda/\Lambda_{\infty} = \frac{46.76}{L_a + L_n} = \frac{46.76}{337.5 + 17.14} = 0.132$$

and consequently the ionisation constant

$$k = \frac{\alpha^2 c}{1 - \alpha} = \frac{(0.132)^2 \times 0.71}{1 - 0.132} = 1.43 \times 10^{-3} \text{ at } 22.8^{\circ}.$$

DISCUSSION

There are, however, some notable peculiarities in the electrochemical behaviour of these two acids. From the formulae given below it will be clear that teresantallic acid (I) may be regarded to be a tri-substituted derivative of acetic acid (II), and tricycloekasantallic acid (III) that of butyric acid (IV). The ionisation constants of these acids and those of some other allied compounds have been compared below (International Critical Table, 1929, Vol. VI, p. 260-300). In the table R stands for the radical represented by Fig. 3.

FIG. 3

Name.	k_i	Temp.	Name.	k_i	Temp.
R-COOH Teresantalic acid (I)	0.69×10^{-5}	22.8°	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOH Valeric acid (VI)	1.56×10^{-5}	25
CH ₃ -COOH Acetic acid (II)	1.813×10^{-5}	25			
R-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOH Tricycloekasantalic acid (III)	1.43×10^{-5}	22.8	CH ₃ \diagup CH-CH ₂ -COOH CH ₃ \diagdown <i>iso</i> Valeric acid (VII)	1.68×10^{-5}	25
CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOH Butyric acid (IV)	1.5×10^{-5}	25			
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$	0.96×10^{-5}	25°	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}-\text{COOH} \end{array}$	1.67×10^{-5}	25
Trimethylacetic acid (V)			Methylethylacetic acid (VIII)		

The ionisation constants of tricycloekasantalic acid (III) and of butyric acid (IV) are nearly of the same order showing thereby that the heavy ring structure, has no direct influence on the ionisation constant of the acid. The case is, however, entirely different with teresantalic acid (I). It being a lower homologue should ordinarily possess higher ionisation constant than that of tricycloekasantalic acid, but the value actually found is only half of that of the latter. It appears, therefore, that in this case the proximity of the ring structure to the tertiary carboxyl group is exerting some dominating influence on the strength of the acid.

The above statement is supported by the following facts that the derivatives of teresantalic acid possessing identical ring structure, *viz.* teresantalol (R-CH₂OH) and teresantalyll chloride (R-CH₂Cl) though contain a primary hydroxyl group and a halogen atom exhibit great steric hindrance, as a result of which it is very difficult to make the hydroxyl group in teresantalol or the halogen atom in teresantalyll chloride to react.

In conformity with the above observations the following facts may also be cited. Among the ordinary fatty derivatives the tertiary compound trimethylacetic acid (V) is the nearest approach to teresantalic acid. Trimethylacetic acid (V) is, however, isomeric with valeric acid (VI), *isovaleric* acid (VII), methylethylacetic acid (VIII), but it possesses a much lower ionisation constant than the others, the ionisation constants of all of which are almost the same. It is already well known that esters of tertiary carboxylic acids like trimethylacetic acid show some resistance towards hydrolysis, the resistance of course decreasing when they are converted into the corresponding primary alcohols or halides. As already indicated teresantalic acid behaves rather differently, its steric hindrance obstinately persists in its derivatives teresantalol and teresantalyll chloride, both of which are not prone to ordinary chemical operations. It is noticeable that the ionisation constant of teresantalic acid is even lower than that of trimethylacetic acid. It is clear, therefore, that there is a direct relationship existing between steric hindrance and strength of acids. This, however, seems to have escaped the notice of earlier workers.

It is interesting to note that the bromine atom of π -bromocamphor (IX), though primary in character, is unusually inert. But when the π -bromocamphor is oxidised to the corresponding bromocamphoric acid (X), the ring undergoing fission, the inactivity of the bromine atom disappears absolutely, so much so, that it undergoes all ordinary chemical reactions with the greatest ease.

It is, therefore, probable that the carboxyl group in teresantallic acid is embedded in the ring structure in a peculiar way which hinders its ionisation and also shields it against outside influences. An X-ray examination of this and similar other compounds so as to determine the relative position and distances of the different atoms and atomic groupings will furnish interesting results. Further work for an exhaustive study of this point is in progress.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
DEPT. OF PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received June 2, 1944.